

THE PERCEPTION OF JOHANNESBURG STOCK EXCHANGE LISTED AND UNLISTED COMPANIES RELATING TO THE WIRELESS OPEN ACCESS NETWORK POLICY DIRECTION

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ABSTRACT

The study investigates the perception of executives in the Johannesburg Stock Exchange listed and unlisted companies regarding the Wireless Open Access Network (WOAN) policy direction released in the year 2019. Since South Africa has a heavy reliance on foreign direct investment, the lack of investor confidence regarding the WOAN policy could affect future investment. The investigation intended to establish the depth of executives' understanding the WOAN policy. The study also uncovers the perceived impact of this policy at decision-making level, where organisational growth strategies are discussed. Similarly, executives expressed a level of interest in championing the WOAN policy-aligned objectives. The purpose of the study was to facilitate a balance between implementing a new policy and securing buy-in from investors. When considering the COVID 19 pandemic and the relationship between connectivity and economic growth, the pandemic escalates the need for connectivity. The research followed a qualitative research methodology, to establish the relationship between executives' perception of WOAN policy and investor confidence. Eight respondents from BCX, Broll Property Group, Volvo South Africa, South African Women in Television Arts, Sanlam Group, Khulasizwe (a subsidiary of Barloworld), BHP Group and VM-Ware participated in the study. Decision-makers from the listed organisations were selected for interviews using a non-probability convenience sampling method. The data analysis process was based on measuring and analysing data collected from the open-ended questionnaire. The results indicated a majority of support for the WOAN policy direction and the objectives of creating inclusivity for Small Medium Enterprises (SME) in the telecommunications industry. In addition, executives would support initiatives presented by SME's that participate in the WOAN. Similarly, some executives provided examples of initiatives that can be adopted to support the WOAN policy direction objectives. It is concluded that the WOAN policy communication media do not reach a wider audience. Accordingly, policy makers are expected to implement this policy diligently and in consultation with decision-makers of organisations that are directly or indirectly affected. Executives believe that connectivity is critical and successful implementation of the WOAN will guide how growth strategies are implemented, in the best interests of overall economic growth.

Keywords: Open Access; connectivity; JSE; stock exchange; South Africa; telecommunication; WOAN.

1. INTRODUCTION

This study focusses on the Department of Telecommunications and Postal Services (DTPS), a division within the government departments of South Africa. All the various departments are guided by the National Development Plan (NDP). Under

this topic, the NDP refers to establishing a “*seamless information infrastructure by 2030 that will underpin a vibrant information society and a knowledge economy that is more inclusive, equitable and prosperous*” (Department of Telecommunication, 2019). The quoted information from the NDP dovetailed with several other policies listed in the WOAN Information Memorandum (IM). The WOAN is a new policy direction proposed by the (DTPS). Following the IM submissions, Independent Communications Authority of South Africa (ICASA, 2019a) launched the emergency 5G spectrum in April 2020, due to the high demand for connectivity during the COVID pandemic. In this context, the emergency spectrum is expected to be revoked by November 31, 2021, after the scheduled announcement by ICASA on August 31 (ICASA, 2021). As it transpires, there are currently delays in implementing the Auction and Wireless Open Access Network spectrum. The plan is for ICASA to finalise their existing legal battles with MTN and Vodacom by 15 September, 2021 (ICASA, 2021). The WOAN policy specifically creates opportunities for select operation on an open access model, as stated in the State of the Nation Address (SONA) (Phakathi, 2019). This means that various businesses not investing in the infrastructure to host the spectrum still have operational access to the Wireless Open Access Network, since the Open Access Network (OAN) is a model that creates inclusivity for businesses that do not have capital (Groenendaal, 2018).

In his January 8 statement, which labelled 2020 as the year for united action to grow South Africa, President Cyril Ramaphosa refers to the “centrally ambitious investment drive”, championed by various events (Arcangeli, 2018; South Africa Investment Conference, 2018; Ramaphosa, 2019). The objective of the initiative is to increase the amount of funding from both local and international investors to secure employment, which makes it critically important to ensure that investors understand new policy that may disrupt the telecommunications sector. The DTPS released a new policy direction statement regarding the Wireless Open Access Network (WOAN) clarifying *inter alia* that the WOAN policy direction both enables and supports the inclusion of Small Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the telecommunications industry (Faku, 2019). The policy will enable SMEs to participate in wholesale mobile connectivity without any capital outlay on spectrum infrastructure. Prior to the WOAN policy direction, spectrum allocation was only given to companies that could afford the capital outlay for infrastructure. According to a study conducted by the University of Stellenbosch in January 2016, the sentiment was that SME’s could be the drivers of economic growth, innovation and job creation. The statement also pointed out that SME’s were major contributors to the GDP (BER, 2016).

In addition to the above, South Africa is exposed to Foreign Holdings, which means that South Africa has above average foreign ownership of local government currency and, thus, an outstanding government debt. It is therefore necessary to harness the support of investors currently operating in the South African economic commercial hub. Fitch Solutions (2020) confirms the level of foreign investment in South Africa.

Significantly, WOAN policy obligations include inclusivity of SME's and simultaneously encourage economic activity. Amongst the objectives of the WOAN policy are enhancing competition in the Information and Communication Technology (ICT) sector and creating a Wireless Open Access Network sharing of infrastructure. The open access industry obligation refers to the allocation of a spectrum licence to Mobile Virtual Network Operators (MVNO's), on the condition that the MVNO's have (at least) a 51 % ownership by previously disadvantaged people. The MVNO's will then be allocated 36 months to utilise the allocated open access licence capacity. The penalty for non-compliance (with the open access industry obligation) may result in withdrawal of the licence by the authority. Whilst the obligations for both industry and WOAN beneficiaries have been stipulated, research findings confirm that South Africa may experience the first deployment of the WOAN policy. Research also confirms that policy uncertainty has a direct relationship with investor confidence. The importance of investors to the South African economy therefore justifies establishing positive investor sentiment (Fitch Solutions, 2020).

South African policy makers refer to Germany as a successful deployment venue, and South Africa has since incorporated some of the strategies used in Germany. However, this development creates concern, since emerging markets reflect poor representation of open access deployments. Indeed, commentary from astute influencers in the investment sphere confirms a negative sentiment regarding specific deployments in areas such as Mexico and South Africa. Trusted investor influencers share negative sentiments in public regarding the open access, while investors' views in South Africa regarding the WOAN are unknown, since this will be the first deployment. According to Fitch Solutions, policy certainty and investor confidence have a direct relationship. In addition, the research establishes distinct perceptions regarding the WOAN policy direction from the eight top executives as participants. Questions relating to the objectives addressed in the study are aimed at establishing the confidence investors have in the WOAN policy and the perceived impact it will have on their business growth strategies. From a social impact perspective, the study reveals that executives are willing to play a role and support those SME's that aim to participate in WOAN. Invariably, the questions posed refer to the perception executives have regarding 5G technology. Since this policy impacts on all industries, the study establishes whether or not executives were closely informed about the policy. This information provides findings that will assist policy makers to ensure that an appropriate response is implemented and that policy does not impact negatively on investor confidence.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The review outlines various topics that have a direct relationship with the impact caused by the WOAN policy direction in relation to acquire Foreign Direct Investments (FDI) to stimulate the economy.

In order for the economy to grow, it is important to understand the impact of key drivers on the economy, where the relevant themes depend on the economic structure of the country, with a focus on South Africa. Those executives who make decisions based on the key themes must share the desired perception regarding the WOAN policy that impacts on all businesses. Research regarding the WOAN policy direction aims to resolve issues relating to inclusivity and connectivity, since these two themes impact directly or indirectly on all businesses, hence the need to establish the perception of the investor community. According to experts, rating agencies such as Fitch ratings, S & P and Moodys evaluate the level of commitment to repaying debt at Company or Country level. The findings also confirm the relationship between the ability to pay debt and investor confidence (Smith, 2013). The ability to repay debt in South Africa, which is the same for every country in the world, is directly reflected in the GDP growth percentage. Significantly, the GDP has the potential to grow, if the WOAN policy is not perceived as a disrupter and therefore serves to delay any organisational growth strategies. When the policy direction was originally announced to the public, commentary from the telecommunications industry leaders was recorded in some instances as unfavourable. Correspondingly, it is noted that the objective of research conducted by Gillwald et al. (2016a, 2016b) was to understand what the impact on costs of data and connection extension would be if open access network strategies were to be implemented. In this study, it is indicated that the perception by major operators such as MTN and Vodacom was that the implementation of the WOAN would be a failure and that it would create an uncertain investor confidence environment (Gillwald et al., 2016b). In his study conducted in Mexico, Roetter (2015) compares South Africa with Mexico. Apart from the fact that South Africa has a population of about 58 million people, while Mexico has approximately 147 million, Roetter was convinced (at that stage) that Mexico had a better chance of successfully deploying the WOAN strategy, because all enabling variables were adhered to, such as the pro-competitive legal framework and the foreign participants included USA, Canadian and Chinese investors with World Bank backing, to name but a few. According to Roetter, it appears that the pieces of the Mexican WOAN puzzle fit together like a glove. While he proposed that South Africa should utilise international resources to help draft the WOAN strategy, he precludes the deployment of the WOAN in SA. Not only did this policy direction tamper with local telecom operators that have international footprints, but it also impacted on the international investor market, hence the need to consolidate the correct perception and issue the appropriate recommendations to the Department of Telecommunications in South Africa. With the negative sentiment already established and the possibility of a decline in investment, the relevance of this topic remains critical.

This research is (therefore) closely concerned with the impact on FDI's of the negative perception regarding the WOAN policy. It is worth noting here that the Business Monitor International (BMI) refers to policy certainty as policy continuity.

Papers by Price Waterhouse Coopers (PWC, 2018a, 2018b) state that the focus on continuity suggests lack of polarisation (i.e. divergent ideologies between different stakeholders) within the political system. Long-term policy continuity would influence FDI inflows by providing a stable and predictable policy environment for the economy and encouraging investment in specific industries that foreign investors find attractive.

In a 2017 article that projected growth for South Africa and other countries, Fitch Solutions refer to political uncertainty as a factor which affects policy and investor confidence. This article confirms the importance of this study, because policy uncertainty is an ongoing concern in the current political climate. Within a contextual understanding of the perceptions of executives who currently operate in the private sector in South Africa, these research findings may assist with policy uncertainty.

Jeffrey Harris (Ko, 2017), a director and chief economist, conducted a study in which he highlighted two important factors that impact on investor confidence, namely: investor trust and policy uncertainty. He believes that investor trust, which he defines as “the willingness to explore investment opportunities and associated intermediation channels available based on their perception of risk and return”, is a dynamic measurement of how investors behave (Ko, 2017). In this context, the Department of Telecommunications also has to use the outcome of the study to ensure that investor trust is established.

2.1 Small Medium Enterprise growth

From the first, it is a known fact that SME's have a great potential to create jobs, where job creation has a direct relationship with economic growth, entrenching the perception that policy will further enable SME's to participate successfully in the telecommunications industry. The discussion report from Statistics South Africa (SSA) released in October 2019 indicated job losses of 141,000 people in the second quarter of 2019. In comparison to 2018, the statistics showed that unemployment increased by 8.6 % (Statistics South Africa, 2019).

The Wireless Open Access Network aims to create opportunity for SME's to operate in the sector without ownership of infrastructure. This will enable participation and broaden the network of businesses that generate revenue and pay taxes. The ripple effect of an increased network of businesses will immediately impact favourably on economic growth. The WOAN policy direction therefore aims to challenge the historical barriers of entry into the telecommunications sector. Directed effort by the DTSPS towards establishing the perception of executives in listed and unlisted companies regarding the WOAN policy will create a thriving environment for SME's.

2.2 Balance of payments in Johannesburg

The historical challenge of negative sentiment towards government can be traced back to (specific) areas in which municipalities are (chronically) indebted. This

debt also includes the private sector, where extended negative sentiment regarding government managed operations could result in a decline in investment. Accordingly, the thrust of this research will assist the DT to manage negative perceptions. For example, the Johannesburg Municipality, one of the largest in South Africa, contributes 18 % to the country's overall GDP. Research conducted between 2016 and 2017 showed that the debt owed to creditors stood at 43 %, including Eskom, private sector service providers, goods and services purchased on credit, where provisions amounted to 13.1%, Bonds to 8.1 % and bank loans to 5.8 % (where the latter included the four major banks in South Africa). It is also recorded (Statistics South Africa, 2018b) that the banks no longer grant new loans to municipalities (Hayes, 2019). This is a clear indication of why it is critically important to establish positive perceptions regarding the WOAN policy, because numerous other failed government/municipal initiatives have underpinned negativity.

2.3 Perception of investors and interdependent topics

It is equally important to understand the perception/s of investors in the private sector, in order to create continued investment interest. Since the banks are no longer lending to municipalities—and the WOAN policy direction was only anticipated to resume in 2021—it is important to establish the confidence levels of investors regarding this policy, more especially on the understanding that the success of a fully connected society depends on its telecommunications infrastructure. Policy makers must therefore establish buy-in from investors regarding this policy. In short, the manner in which the perceptions of potential investors are understood and managed will ensure a healthier economy for South Africa. This statement is endorsed by an article from the Forbes Research Council, which emphasises the need to be proactive, instead of reactive, in managing challenges (Expert Panel, Forbes Coaches Council, 2018).

Before the open access network was introduced, owners of infrastructure such as Vodacom and MTN gave access to other operators in the telecommunication industry, with slanted agreements that prohibited the operator from competitive pricing and/or benefitting from competitive advantage for service delivery (ICASA, 2019b). An invitation for public comment (ICASA, 2019b) emphasised the objectives of the auction process and open access. Public comment is sought/required when an Information Memorandum (IM) is released in the Government Gazette or for download. This response has always targeted industry players who are interested in spectrum allocation. In this particular IM, the differences between the WOAN and auction are clearly specified and the various obligations that govern infrastructure ownership and operation are explained. The fact remains, however, that the “bias” model of operation created barriers of entry. As set out in the ICASA information memorandum, one of the obligations is to influence commercial agreements between infrastructure owners and the WOAN participants. It is also stipulated that, should the WOAN participant not be satisfied, the authorities will assist. This is a clear indication that the bias models of infrastructure owners will ultimately be eliminated

by the WOAN (South African Government, 2012). Once the perception regarding this policy is established, operational inclusion in the main-stream economy will widen for smaller players. What this means is that the general market will trust the services offered by the respective SME in the telecommunications industry. Companies such as VUMATEL have already started participating in the telecommunications space (IT Online, 2014) and will grow further when the WOAN policy is officially managed and governed by the South African regulation system.

2.3.1 Decline in consumer spending

Even though the study aims to establish the perception/s of executives in decision-making roles, background literature suggests that a connected environment will enable potential customers to buy services offered online. It is also evident that companies that are consumer interactive are starting to utilise the online buying method. Should the perception regarding the WOAN not be favourable, organisations could possibly find reasons to disable continuation of the organisation's growth strategies. The assumption is that executives of top performing companies, whether listed or unlisted, will have perceptible influence on the rollout of investment plans. However, if the perceptions about the WOAN policy direction are not favourable for South Africa, the country could encounter economic challenges, which would in turn influence decision-making for implementing growth plans in the nation's respective businesses. Given that businesses that are top-listed and unlisted have established growth strategies for both the long and short term, the objective is to manage the perception/s, in order to maintain the rollout of growth plans of businesses operating in the South African economy.

In research conducted on the impact of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on companies that operate within the insurance industry, PWC found that insurers benefit from using AI for monitoring regulatory requirements when dealing (directly) with clients (Geldenhuys, 2019). Additionally, a report by Deloitte (2020) regarding the insurance regulatory outlook for 2020 states that the scale at which technology is advancing has a direct impact on regulations within the financial services sector, which emphasises the importance of perception regarding the WOAN policy, due to operational reliance within organisations.

Correspondingly, there are three main factors that are affected, the effects of which result in a downturn in the economy. As per the research conducted by PWC, it is clear that uncertainty has a relationship with the decline in consumer spending. What is more, the decline in consumer spending (due to uncertainty) duly inhibits organisational growth and impacts directly or indirectly on all industries (Kupelian & Loughridge, 2016).

2.3.2 Why spectrum policy is critical

A specific PWC study on media, advertising and utilisation of the Internet in South Africa confirms that data usage has grown over the years, while advertising has become increasingly dependent on exposure via mobile platforms. The report highlights the increase in mobile phone utilisation and confirms the increased time

spent online, with an expected growth rate of total Internet and advertising spend at 20.3 %. The report further confirmed an increase in expenditure from 17 billion Rand in 2011 to 45 billion Rand in 2016 in South Africa (De Jager, 2016). Given the current climate of COVID 19, working from home has escalated the need for accessible/reliable WIFI networks. What is more, the working from home paradigm is expected to continue (ILO, 2021).

The five key themes identified for 2020 (Fitch Solutions, 2019b) are as follows:

1. 5G to boost (the) Industrial Internet of Things (IoT) Proliferation;
2. Announcements of joint public-private 4IR initiatives, including smart cities, smart grids, e-government and the promotion of tech in national development plans (Reif, 2018);
3. Regulators that incorporate regulation for technology and streaming as a mean for media and advertising, meaning that older/traditional methods will slowly be affected (Snider, 2019);
4. Utilisation of technology to increase efficiencies and operational strategies;
5. Sustainability in technological usages that require power and other natural resources.

Since these five key themes have a direct relationship with open access networks, the perception of executives in the private sector is vital, because decisions for the listed themes are indirectly driven at the boardroom level. For example, for smart cities to take form, an executive will influence the investment in such a project, or alternatively may even supply the necessary funding. Notably, theme 5 is a critical consideration for new office branches or manufacturing plants.

Similarly to findings published on ITWeb (Mzekandama, 2018), Malinga (2020) confirms the future of quantum physics and the impact it will have on the world of computing. Mr Malinga, an executive at the First National Bank (South Africa), who has access to world class advancement in the ICT, believes that the challenge would be a misaligned perception when the WOAN policy is implemented. The question remains: how will perception of these organisational changes in technology encourage investment? The value chain will be impacted as a result of uncertainty regarding a policy that holds the reins to a successful migration into what the article refers to as “Quantum Supremacy”.

Additionally, research on ITWeb (Mzekandama, 2018) stipulated that market concentration challenges have to be considered when allocating the spectrum. Accordingly, urgent research should evaluate the requirement for the department to undertake a study that will facilitate the forecasting of the growth in the market size for WOAN from 2020–2030. This multi-purpose recommendation will address, inter alia, the current allocation, a predictable increase in population, infrastructure development projects and new technology. Since technology is fast gravitating towards innovative technology, the recommendation is for the department to support research projects that focus on WOAN deployment models, as well as new technology in the telecommunications industry. This proposed support will be

influenced by those executives with a favourable perception regarding the WOAN policy, particularly in the context of the implications of WOAN and how markets will pay attention to the rollout of this policy, prior to deploying their own strategic growth plans.

With regard to the above, while the 5G allocation has yet to be confirmed—and some private entities have already made the upgrade (Dludla, 2020)—the recommendation from ICASA is that 5G *must* take precedence, incorporating the findings of the projected demand spectrum beyond 2020 (Mzekandama, 2018). With these recommendations taken into consideration, the question remains: are investors confident about the WOAN, even with further research required? The above are amongst the concerns that will be tabled in the interviews with executives of listed and unlisted companies.

3. METHODOLOGY

In this study, a qualitative method (Fig. 1) was used to establish the perception of executives in listed and unlisted Johannesburg Stock Exchange (JSE) companies regarding the WOAN policy direction. Qualitative research allows for the identification of new and untouched phenomena. A subset of eight respondents was selected to gather the information. The target population was made up of executives, who were employed within the JSE listed and unlisted companies. The sample population stands poised to provide sentiments and perceptions regarding the policy. Since this sample was carefully selected on the basis of hierarchy within the organisation and the study was cognisant of the typology of the listed and unlisted JSE companies, it was therefore appropriate to stipulate the selection criteria. Each respondent represented a C-Suite occupation in the organisation, with affiliations to various business societies that could expand the reach indirectly at interview stage. The selection had a gender balance, to ensure that established perception was not gender influenced. In relation to the various industries, the selection identified industries such as the automotive, property, mining, financial services, manufacturing and technology sectors that were all likely to be highly reliant on 5G Spectrum, due to market specific activities within their respective industries.

The structure of the questions identified in this study is based on explanatory research. The literature review highlights the importance of this research and aligns with interdependent variables between investor confidence and policy certainty. The primary data collection methodology was used, as the data collected was specifically utilised for this research study.

3.1 Philosophy

The identified philosophy for this study is interpretivism. The nature of the study distinguishes the perception of a specific group of people. The required perspective is from decision makers in organisations, where the researcher acknowledges that perspectives will vary, based on the levels of authority within the respective organisations.

Figure 1. Philosophical considerations. Adapted from Saunders et al. (2013).

3.1.2 Approach

In the inductive approach, which was applied to this study, qualitative data analysis comprises summarising the raw data, differentiating between significant and insignificant information, recognising the important patterns and creating a structure for communicating the heart of what the data reveals. In this qualitative study, the researcher first noted and recorded raw data, then developed information shapes and possible subjects for analysis. Raw data collected by means of semi-structured, face-to-face interviews with eight respondents within various organisations was organised, coded and categorised. The researcher furthermore saw to it that all raw data obtained during interviews was methodically documented, to ensure that nothing was omitted or classified inaccurately. The stored data was subsequently analysed and represented schematically in terms of codes, categories and emerging themes.

3.1.3 Methodology

The qualitative methodology adopted for this study provided a heightened understanding of individuals' attitudes and executives' perspectives regarding the WOAN.

3.1.4 Exploratory research

Investigating the perception of executives in this context directed the researcher to apply the principles of exploratory research. According to Kumar (2011), exploratory research is undertaken with the objective either of exploring an area where little is known, or to investigate the possibilities of undertaking a particular research study when the direction of the investigation is new and there is a lack of adequate data about the problem at hand.

3.2 Sampling strategy

The target population refers to all the members who meet the criterion specified for a research investigation (Zikmund et al., 2010). In this case, the target population of this study comprised executives of listed and unlisted companies, i.e. skilled employees within organisations that operate in the Johannesburg area. A target population is identified on the basis that the population fits the criteria of decision makers who influence organisational growth strategies. The participants targeted as the sample of this study were eight executives of listed and unlisted companies, which represents a reasonable sample in qualitative studies. Executives operating in South Africa were selected on the assumption that any investment decision would be discussed in their presence. This sample has the capacity to delay investment in SA if the perception regarding the WOAN policy is not favourable, or otherwise to expedite investment in areas not previously considered profitable or practical. It was therefore important for the study to engage with and acquire perceptions from these leaders who influence business strategy. Friedberg (2018) provides a glimpse into emerging markets and reiterates the high risk and volatility of investing in them. This, therefore, highlights the potential of policy such as the WOAN to delay investment decisions.

This study followed a non-probability sampling method, with the identified method of sampling being convenience sampling, since the nature of the study requires a specific sample frame that will provide valuable information that can be considered for the findings. The sample frame took into account the levels of authority of individuals in top listed and unlisted companies.

3.3 Interviews

A total of eight interviews were completed with executive personnel. Interviewees were granted confidentiality and the freedom to express their views regarding the topic without fear of judgment. Saunders et al. (2013) confirm that building an understanding with participants is easiest with face-to-face interviews. The eight face-to-face, semi-structured, open-ended interviews commenced with a few demographic questions, then moved onto questions deriving from the literature and finished with open-ended questions.

Two interviewing techniques were used, viz., note taking and audio recording. Participants were asked demographic and open-ended questions to explore their beliefs, values, understandings, feelings, experiences and perspectives on the WOAN issues.

Demographics questions:

1. How long have you been in top executive positions?
2. Have you worked in other countries apart from SA?
3. How long have you been working for this company?
4. What is your previous job description?

The objective of the next four questions is to establish the perceptions of key decision makers within top JSE listed and unlisted companies to ensure the Government has support regarding the WOAN policy implementation from the economic hub of South Africa.

5. Do you support the WOAN policy direction and the change it brings to the telecommunications industry? Are you confident that the policy will add value to your organisation growth strategy? And why? If no, why?
6. Do you have enough information regarding the WOAN policy direction? If yes, why? If no, why?
7. The WOAN policy is going to give smaller businesses the opportunity to participate in the open access network. The main objective of the policy direction is not only to create access but to influence the cost of data through effective wholesale regulation. Do you think the open access network will create inclusivity of SME's? If yes, how? If no, why?
8. It is common for global organisations to have a mentorship programme or to provide funding opportunities for small medium enterprises. These programmes sometimes fall under the Corporate Social Investment (CSI). Does this organisation have an SME upliftment/support programme?

The objective for the four questions below is to determine how open the key decision makers are to support this initiative through investing in micro/medium enterprises such as SMME's.

9. Long-term company strategy dictates the desirable actions for the said organisation. In this case, long-term investment opportunities would be discussed in board meetings. Do you think that investing in a small enterprise operating in the telecommunications sector would be considered by your organisation? If yes, why? If no, why not?
10. Has your organisation either funded a small enterprise or invested in one? If yes, why? If no, why not?
11. Since the digital era is upon us, most companies have to rely on connectivity or data, for example, the data calling, internet, 5G. Some businesses also experience gains if their consumers have access to a cheaper cost of data. With the knowledge of your current growth strategies, will extended fast connectivity benefit your organisation and why?
12. How would your organisation benefit from an increased number of consumers having access to connectivity?

The objective for the last four questions is to establish the impact of the new

allocation of the (5G) spectrum in growing the JSE listed and unlisted companies’/ other activities towards revenue growth.

13. How would your organisation benefit from an increased number of consumers having access to connectivity?
14. Has this organisation ever considered participating as a business in the tele-communications industry? This question is posed in order to establish if the telecommunication sector is at all an industry of interest for investment for the organisation. This is to establish the sentiment regarding the WOAN, particularly if the growth path for the organisation is in the communication’s space.
15. Do you think the Government is proactively considering views from the private sector regarding connectivity? And why?
16. Given an opportunity to engage personnel within the WOAN consortium that will be appointed to draft the WOAN structure and process, would you want to participate and represent private sector interest? If yes, how would you prefer to participate?
17. What would your overall recommendation to government be with reference to the topic?

3.4 Data analysis technique

The above steps provide a structured and systematic way of organising and preparing data for analysis (transcribing interviews), reading through all collected data, coding all of the collected data, how the themes and description will be presented in the qualitative narrative and finally interpreting the results or findings that describe a particular phenomenon (Fig. 2; Creswell, 2014).

The qualitative data was analysed from the transcripts into codes, with arising categories and the development of emerging themes. Since qualitative research does not address the issue of validity and reliability (Lincoln et al., 2011) which pertains more to quantitative data analysis, it is appropriate to address how qualitative research establishes alternative constructs in the form of trustworthiness and its sub-constructs.

3.5 Limitations of the study

Qualitative research and its associated methods cannot provide a large amount of information in a timely manner from a reasonable sized sample, when compared to quantitative methods. This research is no different, in that it involved executives who are extremely busy and cannot easily allocate time for interviews. The sample size is only eight participants and cannot be stretched beyond that because of the time allocated for this study and availability of the level of executives profiled to participate. The assumption is that this study has identified the required number of participants. The limitation is that some executives may engage with enthusiasm and provide in-depth information that may lead to the opportunity for extended recommendations.

Figure 2. Data analysis in qualitative research. Source: Creswell (2014).

4. Findings of the study

4.1 Demographic information

Demographics by gender aims to clarify the split between participants, with limited significance to the study. Of the total number of participants, there were two female participants, who represented 25 % of the sample, and eventually seven male participants, who represented 87.5 %. Approximately 30 to 40 minutes were spent with each participant during the face-to-face interviews.

4.2 Experience in the industry

All respondents are currently in the top executive positions (Table 1), with 75 % of the participants having over 10 years of experience in executive positions and the remaining 25 % having between 5–9 years of experience. Question 2 established the work experience in other parts of the world, apart from SA. This international experience will facilitate a broader perspective by incorporating global business knowledge.

Table 1. The level of experience of participants and the summary of the statistics.

Number of participants	8
Years in top executive positions	Less than 10 years (12.5 %)
Years in top executive positions	Over 10 years (75.0 %)
Years working for company	2 years and less (12.5 %) 5 years and more
International experience excluding SA	Yes (87.0 %) – No (12.5 %)

The participants were drawn from listed and unlisted companies. All the participants are employed by their various organisations. The majority (75 %) of the participants hold positions of Managing Director, Chief Executive Officer or Executive Director, while the remaining 25 % are Senior Executives.

Table 2. A summary of the years of service of the respondents.

Years of service	Service, in %
>1–5	12.6 %
6–10	62.0 %
11–15	12.6 %
>20	12.6 %

4.3.1 Core themes

The data analysis results yielded the following core themes:

1. Limited knowledge regarding the WOAN policy direction;
2. Dissatisfaction regarding the (historical) exclusion of medium size businesses in the telecommunications industry;
3. Modest desire to invest in the telecoms industry, because it is not an industry focus aligned to their organisations;
4. 5G is perceived as a luxury by the general SA market, because 4G and 3G are still more relevant;
5. An increase in connectivity for consumers to drive growth in sales and profitability;
6. Continued engagement between private and public sector is important.

Research objective 1: To establish perceptions of key decision makers within top JSE listed and unlisted companies in order to ensure Government has support regarding the WOAN policy implementation from the economic hub.

Key findings:

1. Executives of listed and unlisted companies support the new model of the WOAN policy direction. The perception acquired resonates with the general objectives of the WOAN policy.

Respondent 007

“I can't say I was bothered because I wasn't aware of this particular development but by all means, the notion that we are trying to open it up to more players, just in the realm of competition alone is a step in the right direction because when you have 2 or 3 or even 10 dominant players in an industry it doesn't allow for effective competition and really passing down the value to the end user”.

2. The respondents demonstrated a keen interest to support SME's that operate in the telecommunications sector. The support can only be granted if it is aligned to the industry in which the respective businesses operate.

Respondent 006

“Well like I said, this company has been born of opportunity and empowerment. My mandate would be to ensure that everybody that I supply with or work with of any sort is to ensure that vein is carried on through the opportunity that has come through from a Khulasiswe perspective. So yes, that is definitely my answer that it is to work with smaller companies or to be able to give opportunity from a CSI perspective once we have obviously established ourselves”.

3. The respondents were not fully exposed to WOAN policy and would appreciate having more information regarding policies that affect all businesses directly or indirectly.

Respondent 005

“If it's not in my industry I'm going to see it, I'm going to give you an example with Khulasizwe transaction, it was everywhere, it was everywhere like people would read the stats. They intently said, “We are going to catch people's eyes, and that's what you need to do for this type of policy it's such a crucial thing for the rest of South Africa. There needed to be a bit more in terms of attracting people's attention, the right people the various industries would be able to say, hey wake up, this is what is going on”.

Research objective 2: To determine how willing key decision makers are to support the WOAN policy and associated initiatives by investing in SMMEs.

Key findings:

1. The question that referred to 5G licensing stimulated conversation, but the findings demonstrate that respondents understand the government decision to delay the licensing. It was also evident that the social impact of connecting people in remote areas was a greater concern. 4G and 3G connectivity must be a focus in those areas.

Respondent 006

“So obviously the aim is connectivity, in terms of, we need to get to a certain level. I think as a country and I think you mention a very important point there that, in the rural areas, people are not really going to be buying an S10 device that is 5G ready and all that stuff, so yes I think we’re in a catch 22 situation because there is a population in South Africa that is still rapidly moving and wanting to stay in touch with the rest of the world but then the problem like you are saying, in an area where or in a country where we are still sort of working to get there and there is a reliance even from the rural side, we are now sending the information from a 5G to somebody who cannot access it, so there is a danger of a loss of information because that person cannot access it because they are not there yet. I think the aim is that we would need to try and get to a level where we are at the least as a country all functioning on devices that all speak to either a 4G so that the correct information can then be transferred and all of that and the accessibility is available to more than a 40% of the nation, then planning toward 5G. Yes, I fully agree with it because we can’t sit on our laurels.”

2. Respondents expressed the lack of spectrum as a concern, but do not see a direct relationship between the WOAN policy (connectivity) and short term profits of their organisations.

Respondent 009

“I think look in business connectivity let’s say between the different sets of the business there is definitely avenue for value creation, there you have systems that communicate with each other, systems are everywhere, you can communicate quicker your analysis systems. Whether there is benefit that improves your bottom line, significantly, I’m not sure”.

Research objective 3: To establish the impact of the new allocation of the spectrum in growing the JSE listed and unlisted companies and promoting other activities favouring revenue growth.

Key findings:

1. Respondents appreciate the means by which input regarding government policy change is conducted. However, the requirement for face-to-face discussions for input from the private sector is regarded as lacking, particularly on policy changes that impact on investor confidence and indeed on all industries.

Respondent 004

“Policy at government level is supposed to address the inequalities of the past. Communication is the fastest way to build an economy.”

4. Conclusions and Recommendation

4.1 Conclusions

The study presents a conclusion that there was a lack of communication with the private sector towards establishing the WOAN policy. The department of tele-

communications misrepresented the proposed policy direction draft for comment to the public. A greater communications effort was required in order to include other industry players, because the telecommunications infrastructure affects all business. The respondents echoed uncertainty towards implementation of the WOAN policy. In this light, the capability and capacity of Government were questioned.

In addition, respondents identify the need for the WOAN policy. Characteristics of the WOAN resonate with the respondents. Even though a clear action strategy to support SME's does not exist, the willingness to support them *does* exist. The willingness from the private sector is an opportunity to be explored creatively.

Notwithstanding the need for infrastructure, growth strategies were acknowledged to have an indirect relationship with the WOAN policy. Growth strategies may be impacted on by the uncertain future regarding this new policy. Usage of 5G networks appeared to be supported from the perspective of technology advancement. However, respondents quickly alluded to democratic views, which include supporting the department of Telecommunications for not issuing the 5G dedicated allocation focus. The need to connect a higher number of people in rural and township areas, at a low cost, remains a priority.

This study has given an indication of the perception executives have regarding the WOAN and provided greater insight into the impact of a negative perception. The findings have indicated that the participation of small businesses in the telecommunications industry *is* supported by investors. The listed objectives in Chapter One and the overall findings have resulted in an opportunity to implement further activity that will restore the levels of investor confidence. The five key themes highlighted by Fitch Solutions (2020) have been supported by literature reviewed during the course of the study. The listed themes have a direct relationship with growth strategies for businesses. It is heartening to learn that the perception of the WOAN policy direction is supported and, most importantly, that it has great potential to create employment by mobilising distinct collaboration within the private sector.

4.2 Recommendations

4.2.1 Clear and rational conclusions based on primary and secondary findings

According to the findings, the executives were exposed to limited information regarding the WOAN policy direction. What transpired is that 85 % of the responses confirmed knowledge about the telecommunication sector and the barrier to entry. In addition, the discussion evolved towards support of SME's. Respondents shared views about SME programmes that are active in their firms. While 100 % of the respondents have existing programmes to support SMEs, the support is, however, aligned to the industry in which the company operates. With all the resistance demonstrated, specific industries indicated the possibility of creating opportunity for the telecom-driven SME to receive support from their organisations. The findings, which presuppose a positive mindset from the executives, show that the biggest hindrance to supporting telecom-driven SME's was the affiliated industry of ope-

ration. The mining and automotive sector had opportunities to render services in communities they operate in and telecommunications can be added to the list of methods used to empower communities. The other key theme discussed is whether executives are willing to participate in forums that influence policy. The findings also indicated that the private sector is willing to assist government policy changes and will support implementation. The sentiment was shared that Government needs to engage the private sector proactively, particularly on policy that impacts on all industries. Government must further act on the input received from the respective engagement platforms.

The department of telecommunications must gain access to a wider network of decision makers and deploy efficient processes to engage with executives, such as digital platforms regarding the WOAN policy.

In addition, webinar themes must focus on the WOAN policy direction and the changes initiated by the COVID-19 pandemic. Participation of businesses can be tabled in these forums. It is advised that the DTSP should set up a think-tank team that consists of a marketing, technical, technology innovation and the Corporate Social Investment (CSI) personnel. This think-tank should be headed by an individual who has overall experience of the WOAN policy. The think-tank team can then establish a proposition to mining companies and request CSI collaboration, which could leverage the usage of funds allocated by the mining company for empowerment activities.

4.2.2 A networked society

This recommendation is influenced by the findings that anchored the lack of comprehension regarding the impact of telecommunications infrastructure in various industries. The DTSP should make statistics and reports available that can inform executives. For the purpose of building trust and a relationship with private sector, the DTSP should engage consulting agencies and acquire statistics and reports from research findings regarding the impact of connectivity per respective industry. If the relevant research is not available, the DTSP should invest in conducting the (necessary) research by acquiring partners to facilitate it. With this in mind, the findings of the study can be used to communicate relevant information creatively, with a view to facilitating networking in the private sector listed in the acquired database. This information can also be used to target industries that have a proven high dependency on—and a high usage potential of—suitable telecommunications infrastructure. Validated and factual research information will inform executives' perspective and provide justification to motivate the[ir] board of directors to invest more in SME's that operate in the telecommunications industry.

The DTSP must be agile in policy changes, since the telecommunications industry is a highly innovative industry and constant developments are taking place around the globe via input from the likes of Google and Facebook. The DTSP must form an alliance with Google and Facebook and be a step ahead of developments in Africa that need to be piloted relating to connectivity.

The DTPS must establish a further relationship with Kenya and acquire data regarding the LOON connectivity method piloted by Google in Kenya. This will represent a substantial value add, but since the WOAN policy is still in the final stages of formulation, a clause must be added to enable easy adoption innovation in the telecommunications sector. This type of information must be communicated to executives in order to boost investor confidence and to keep pace with innovation in developed markets.

5. Further research

This study has just “scratched” the surface, in terms of research conducted in relation to the WOAN. This means that, while the findings indicate a trend in perception regarding the WOAN policy, further research will potentially enable/expedite action towards resolving some of the current challenges. For the purposes of completing the knowledge of perceptions regarding the WOAN policy, it is advised that focussed research be conducted on SME’s that operate in the telecommunications industry, because these SME’s are going to be an integral part of the success of the WOAN. The findings, which will assist DTPS to meet the requirements and expectations of SME’s, may also expose lack of understanding, so that the DTPS may start the process of teaching and informing interested players in the industry. Most important, however, is informed management of expectations from the SME market.

The DTPS must further link up with Facebook and Google organisations regarding telecommunication developments such as the LOON technology used in Kenya (Westgarth, 2020).

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